

TEACHER'S PERSPECTIVE ON TECHNOLOGY INTEGRATION ON CONTINUING PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT (C.P.D.): A VISTA FROM GENERATIVE CHANGE MODEL

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Teacher's Perspective on Technology Integration on Continuing Professional Development (C.P.D.): A Vista from Generative Change Model

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Abstract

Education is a prerequisite for the development of a country. The teacher is the backbone of the education system and is the architect of society. The progress of an organization depends upon the quality of its teachers. Today's child is tomorrow's citizen of the country. To prepare efficient teachers in the 21st century, teacher educators need to be constantly top-notch in their profession. As a way of dealing with this problem, this Qualitative research aimed to explore the perspectives of teachers using technology. Also, this study involved purposive sampling of 12 teachers from the selected public schools in the six districts of Manila. Furthermore, data from this study were used as a framework for developing the Continuing Professional Development (C.P.D.). Data were gathered through online survey forms and face-to-face online interviews utilizing the researcher-made guide questions. The perceived responses were then carefully described and analyzed. The findings of the study revealed that the collective themes emphasize the importance of reflection, critique, and personal voice in the generative change model for technology integration in teacher professional development (CPD). This approach fosters individual teacher growth and innovation by encouraging reflection and introspection to develop a deeper understanding of technology use and more effective teaching strategies, providing, and receiving critique to refine and improve practice, empowering teachers to advocate for necessary changes and resources through leveraging their personal voice. Overall, this holistic approach promotes innovative CPD strategies that are responsive to the evolving landscape of educational technology.

Keywords: *continuing professional development, purposive sampling technique, 21st century*

Introduction

Education is crucial for a country's development, and teachers are the education system's and society's backbone. An organization's success depends on the quality of its teachers. Today's students are the future citizens of the country. To prepare effective teachers for the 21st century, educators must continuously excel through ongoing professional development (C.P.D.). C.P.D. involves various activities (formal, non-formal, and informal) aimed at enhancing teachers' knowledge, confidence, attitudes, values, interests, skills, and competencies. This continuous development ensures that teachers can adapt to changing times and meet the evolving needs of students and society.

Continuing professional development (C.P.D.) is vital in a university setting, fostering professional and personal growth while enhancing teaching and learning. One of the significant challenges educational institutions face today is ensuring that students develop the skills and competencies necessary to succeed in contemporary society. This endeavor is challenging in the fast-changing world, where labor instability, mobility, demographic transition, and the globalized economy continuously redefine society's needs and aspirations (Ahmad et al., 2021). Amid these changes, teachers must continuously validate and upgrade their skills to help students become competent, competitive, and socially integrated individuals.

Research Objectives

The research focuses on understanding teachers' perspectives in using technology and developing a C.P.D. framework for educational technology integration. It aims to provide insights into teachers' experiences, identify gaps in their knowledge and skills, create a comprehensive framework, inform C.P.D. strategies, and enhance teacher professional growth, ultimately benefiting students and the educational system. Specifically, it aimed to:

1. investigate teachers' perspectives on technology use;
2. analyze the interplay between personal, behavioral, and environmental factors;
3. explore teachers' learning and development through the lens of the generative change model and
4. develop a technology-based framework based on the study findings.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative research method, particularly Grounded Theory. This design is well suited to study the perspectives and experiences of teachers in the selection, planning, and execution of teachers' professional development programs. According to Creswell (2017), qualitative research is an inquiry process of understanding based on distinct methodological traditions of inquiry that explore a social or human problem.

Grounded theory emphasizes theoretical sensitivity toward emergent empirical data through data emersion with a fundamental focus on contextual understandings and relevance, according to La Rossa (2015), especially within qualitative research studies. This allows explicit and implicit data to emerge while identifying patterns and data connections (Glaser, 1992). Additionally, it permits the research to shift from concentrating on generalizability and verification to concentrating on comprehending what is happening in the research topic through an inductive process. A fundamental tenet of grounded theory is theoretical sampling, which necessitates reflexivity, questioning insight, and reflection on the researcher's part. Using this strategy, research can be flexible and respond to new information rather than following a sequential methodology.

Draucker et al. (2017) mentioned that this is especially crucial because the problem's dynamics and the facts that can surface are still hidden, ambiguous, and deeply embedded in an implicit social context. According to Charmaz (2014), an approach to data analysis that is flexible enough to allow for greater flexibility in analyzing emerging data and understanding the underlying problem is deemed desirable. This would enable the researcher to fine-tune the methodology to fit the research context. When further developed and refined based on the available data, the core category allows a problem-relevant data-grounded explanatory theory to emerge, allowing this thesis to understand the underlying phenomenon and provide an appropriate framework and direction for action.

The choice of a qualitative approach resulted from realizing that a qualitative framework would help achieve the general goals of this research and better enable the exploration of decision-making inefficiencies within a contextual setting. The paradigm of qualitative research is becoming more and more popular in the fields of organizational phenomena and management.

Respondents

The study was conducted in the 12 public elementary schools in the six districts of Manila, the distribution of which is shown in Table 1 below:

Table 1. School Participants per District

<i>District</i>	<i>School</i>
I	Gen. Vicente Lim Elementary School Juan Nolasco High School
II	F.G. Calderon Int. Elementary School F. G. Calderon Integrated H.S.
III	Juan Sumulong Elementary School Jose Abad Santos High School
IV	Graciano Lopez-Jaena ES Claro M. Recto High School
V	Justo Lukban Elementary School Manuel A. Roxas High School
VI	Bagong Barangay Elementary School Carlos P. Garcia High School

For this study, the researcher used the purposive sampling technique, in which he identified the twelve (12) teachers from selected schools in districts 1-6, Manila, where the interview and data gathering shall be conducted.

Purposive sampling includes a collection of non-probability sampling methods whereby entities are deliberately chosen based on specific features that align with the researcher's sample requirements. Purposive sampling involves the deliberate selection of individuals.

The researcher identified 12 participants in the study based on their age and years of service. Table 2 shows the distribution of participants in the research.

Table 2. Teacher Participants per District

<i>District</i>	<i>School</i>	<i>Number of Participants</i>
I	Gen. Vicente Lim Elementary School	1
	Juan Nolasco High School	1
II	F.G. Calderon Int. Elementary School	1
	F. G. Calderon Integrated H.S.	1
III	Juan Sumulong Elementary School	1
	Jose Abad Santos High School	1
IV	Graciano Lopez-Jaena ES	1
	Claro M. Recto High School	1
V	Justo Lukban Elementary School	1
	Manuel A. Roxas High School	1
VI	Bagong Barangay Elementary School	1
	Carlos P. Garcia High School	1
Total		12

Instrument

In this study, structured interview guides for teachers were constructed by the researcher and checked and validated by experts in the field. They consisted of open-ended questions, ensuring responses were not limited and that other questions arose as soon as responses were given. Open-ended questions allow participants to respond on their terms rather than providing them with a prepared list of possible answers. In exploratory investigations and qualitative research methodologies, open-ended questions are frequently employed. Qualitative studies that utilize open-ended questions allow researchers to take a holistic and comprehensive look at the studied issues. Open-ended responses permit respondents to provide more options and opinions, giving the data more diversity than possible with a closed-question or forced-choice survey. This entry expands on the many benefits of open-ended survey questions before examining the steps to writing well-constructed open-ended questions.

To guarantee the study's validity and reliability, strategies such as member checking—where participants validated the accuracy of their interview summaries and the thematic interpretations—and triangulation were employed by comparing data from interviews and observations. This meticulous approach to data analysis aimed to ensure the findings authentically represented the teachers' perspectives in using technology and developing a C.P.D. framework for educational technology integration.

Procedure

The researcher wrote a letter to the Schools Division Superintendent of Manila to ask permission to conduct the research at 12 schools in Manila.

With the approval permission, the researcher wrote a letter to school principals, asking them to allow him to conduct the study and administer the interview at their most convenient time. With their permission, the survey interview was conducted using an audio recorder. The completed interviews were subject to be confidential, and their responses were subjected to review to make sure that the data needed were answered correctly.

The interviewees were asked regarding the language in which they felt most comfortable expressing themselves. The researcher documented the non-verbal and verbal reactions.

The researcher documented the nonverbal clues and gestures observed throughout the interview, whereas the participants' verbatim responses were captured on audio and transcribed after the session. The participants were also offered discussions following the mentioned interview.

The respondents' suggestions and recommendations regarding the enhancement of the study were incorporated into the concluding chapter of the research output.

The gathered data were processed by tallying, analysis, and interpretation.

Ethical Considerations

Bhandari (2021) views ethical considerations in research as a set of principles that govern the design and practice of research. Scientists and researchers must adhere to a specific protocol when collecting data from people. Human research aims to understand the nature of life, study effective treatments, investigate behavior, and improve the quality of life in other ways. What you decide and how you study it involve critical ethical considerations. These considerations include protecting the rights of research participants, increasing the validity of the research, and maintaining scientific integrity.

Results and Discussion

This section provides the analysis and interpretation of data gathered by the researcher.

Teachers' Perspectives on Technology Use

Theme 1: Reciprocal Determinism

The theme of reciprocal determinism within the context of technology use in education illustrates a sophisticated interplay between the teaching environment and the educators. This dynamic is crucial in understanding how technological integration in professional development is not merely a matter of access to tools but also profoundly influenced by the culture and ethos of the educational setting as well as the proactive behavior of teachers.

Environment's Influence on Technology Use: The statements from the respondents highlight how an environment that fosters a culture of innovation and continuous improvement can significantly enhance the adoption of technology. For instance, when the teaching environment is conducive to experimentation and supported by a philosophy of ongoing improvement, as noted by Respondent 4, it naturally encourages educators to embrace technological tools. This support can come in various forms, including access to the latest digital tools, administrative encouragement to try new methods, or institutional priorities that favor innovative teaching practices. Furthermore, the perspective that learners are paramount, as expressed by Respondent 1, underscores that technology is seen as a facilitation tool and a critical enhancer of the learning experience, thereby pushing its adoption as a core component of educational

strategies.

Teachers' Influence on the Technological Environment: Conversely, teachers play a pivotal role in shaping the technological landscape of their educational environments. Their individual decisions to integrate technology, driven by a commitment to providing the best possible education, act as a catalyst for broader changes within their institutions. For example, Respondent 1's active choice to use technology as a critical component of teaching methodology reflects a personal initiative that can influence peers and decision-makers within the school to recognize and support the use of such tools. Similarly, Respondent 5's technology integration into the operational workflow demonstrates how teachers' technology adoption can lead to structural changes in education delivery, thereby gradually transforming the educational process.

This reciprocal determinism between the environment and the teachers illustrates that adopting and effectively using technology in education depends on both external support and internal motivation. The environment must enable and support technological innovation, while teachers must actively engage with and advocate for these tools to maximize their potential. This bidirectional influence ensures that technology integration becomes a sustainable and evolving part of the educational fabric, driven by both top-down support and bottom-up initiative. Understanding and nurturing this reciprocal relationship is critical to fostering environments where technology integration can thrive, enhancing teaching practices and student outcomes.

Theme 2. Behavioral Capability:

Behavioral capability emphasizes the essential skills and knowledge teachers need to integrate technology into their professional development effectively. The responses reflect a spectrum of comfort levels with technology, with some teachers feeling well-equipped and others recognizing a need for further training. For instance, a teacher who mentioned being 65% comfortable highlights a significant but incomplete comfort level, indicating a gap that could be filled with targeted training. This need for ongoing professional development is crucial because as technology evolves, so must educators' skills and competencies. Furthermore, another respondent's difficulty coping with new technologies underscores the challenge of keeping up with rapid technological advances. Effective C.P.D. programs must, therefore, address these disparities by providing comprehensive training that enhances teachers' technical skills and confidence. This will improve their efficacy in using technology and empower them to explore and implement innovative educational tools and methods.

Theme 3. Observational Learning

As evident in the responses, observational learning is a crucial method through which teachers acquire new technological skills and integrate them into their teaching. Teachers often adopt new tools and methods after observing their effectiveness in their peers' classrooms, highlighting the critical role of a collaborative and open educational environment where such observational learning can occur. This peer-to-peer learning is facilitated by workshops, shared teaching sessions, and informal exchanges, which help spread innovative practices and reduce the apprehension of adopting new technologies. For instance, a teacher learning from colleagues during workshops exemplifies how direct observation and shared experiences can significantly influence one's teaching practices. Such dynamics underscore the importance of creating opportunities within schools for teachers to observe and learn from each other, thereby enhancing the collective technological capability of the faculty.

Theme 4. Reinforcements

Reinforcements play a pivotal role in shaping teachers' ongoing use of technology. Positive feedback from students and colleagues is a strong motivator, encouraging teachers to continue exploring and using new technologies. Conversely, negative experiences, such as technical failures or lack of support, can deter them from further use. For example, positive student feedback reinforces the teacher's use of interactive tools, highlighting the importance of supportive and constructive feedback mechanisms. Therefore, schools should create environments where positive reinforcements are expected, and teachers feel supported in their technological endeavors. This could include recognition from the administration for successful technology integration, structured feedback sessions, and peer support systems.

Theme 5. Expectations

Expectations regarding the impact of technology use in education significantly influence teachers' motivation and engagement with technological tools. When teachers see that technology meets or exceeds their expectations in facilitating learning and engagement, it reinforces their usage and integration into the classroom. This fulfillment of expectations builds confidence and encourages further exploration and adoption of new technologies. However, when expectations are not met, it can lead to disillusionment and reduced use. Managing expectations through realistic goal setting and providing adequate training and resources is crucial to ensure teachers feel equipped and supported. Schools must strive to align the capabilities of technology with teachers' expectations, ensuring that both instructional needs and educational outcomes are effectively met.

Theme 6. Self-Efficacy

Self-efficacy, or teachers' confidence in their ability to use technology effectively, is critical to their engagement with technological tools in education. Teachers with high self-efficacy are more likely to embrace and utilize technology innovatively. This confidence

often stems from successful past experiences and adequate support, including training and resources. For instance, a teacher expressing growing confidence in technology use highlights the role of familiarity and positive outcomes in building this self-efficacy. Enhancing self-efficacy can significantly impact technology integration in teaching. It suggests that C.P.D. programs focus on skill development and creating experiences that build and reinforce teachers' confidence in their technological capabilities.

Interplay Between Personal, Behavioral, and Environmental Factors

To comprehensively discuss the interplay of personal, behavioral, and environmental factors affecting technology integration in teachers' professional development, we can delve deeper into how these factors dynamically influence each other. Each theme is pivotal in understanding how educators adapt to and incorporate technological tools within their professional practices.

Theme 1: Personal Factors

Personal factors encompass teachers' individual beliefs, motivations, and prior experiences with technology. These factors critically shape their willingness and approach to integrating technology into their teaching. Teachers with positive experiences and a strong belief in the benefits of technology are more likely to pursue and advocate for its use. For example, a teacher mentioned, "I have always seen technology as a gateway to engaging my students more effectively," highlighting how personal enthusiasm can drive technological adoption. Another noted, "My previous successes with interactive learning tools boost my confidence in using new technologies," which shows the impact of positive experiences on future technology use. However, not all experiences are positive; as one teacher pointed out, "I have been burned by software crashes during lessons, which makes me cautious." Such experiences can instill a sense of hesitation, impacting their openness to new technologies. Other responses include, "I believe technology can sometimes distract more than it helps," reflecting skepticism, and "I am excited about any new tech that saves time," showing a pragmatic approach to technology adoption.

Theme 2: Behavioral Factors

Behavioral factors involve teachers' actions and efforts to learn and integrate technology. This includes attending training, experimenting with new tools, and sharing knowledge with peers. One teacher shared, "I make it a point to attend at least two tech workshops every semester to stay updated," indicating proactive behavior in skill enhancement. Another said, "I often try out new apps first on my own before introducing them in the classroom," demonstrating a methodical approach to technology integration. Additionally, "I share successful digital strategies in our monthly teaching meetings" shows how teachers' behaviors contribute to a broader cultural shift towards technology use in schools. Responses such as "I have started using quizzes and interactive modules more frequently after seeing positive results" and "I sometimes revert to traditional methods when technology feels overwhelming" illustrate the varying degrees of behavioral engagement with technology based on personal comfort and perceived efficacy.

Theme 3: Environmental Factors

Environmental factors refer to the external conditions that facilitate or hinder technology adoption, such as institutional support, available infrastructure, and the overall educational policy environment. One teacher stated, "Our school's investment in a new learning management system has been a game changer," highlighting how resource allocation can enhance technology integration. Another observed, "Lack of timely tech support is a major barrier in using more sophisticated tools," pointing out infrastructural limitations. Further, "The administration's push for digital classrooms has motivated many of us to rethink our teaching methods" reflects how policy and leadership can drive technology adoption. More insights include, "Peer encouragement and shared tech resources in our teacher's lounge inspire experimentation" and "We need more in-school training sessions to utilize available technology fully," both underscore the school environment's critical role in supporting or restricting technology use.

These themes underscore a complex ecosystem where personal beliefs and experiences, behavioral actions, and the surrounding environment interact to shape how technology is adopted and used in educational settings. For effective integration of technology, it is crucial that educational policies and school environments not only provide the necessary resources and support but also align with and reinforce teachers' positive behavioral and personal factors. This alignment helps create a robust framework where technology can seamlessly integrate into teaching practices, enhancing educator and student experiences.

Teachers' Learning and Development Through the Lens of the Generative Change Model

This objective examines the influence of the generative change model on teachers' adoption and integration of technology in their professional development. The generative change model, emphasizing reflection, introspection, critique, and personal voice, offers a framework for understanding how teachers can continuously evolve their teaching practices through active engagement with technology.

Theme 1: Reflection

Reflection involves teachers looking back on their experiences with technology and assessing what works well and what does not. This process is crucial for continuous improvement in technology use. Teachers reported, "Reflecting on my lessons helps me understand the impact of technology on student engagement," illustrating how reflection allows for evaluating technology's effectiveness in the classroom. Another noted, "Regular reflection sessions have prompted me to adjust my approach to digital tools," highlighting how

this practice leads to better alignment of technology with pedagogical goals. Additionally, responses like "I reflect after every session to note down successes and failures" and "Reflection has become a part of my daily routine to enhance my teaching with tech" show that systematic reflection is integral to mastering technology use.

Theme 2: Introspection

Introspection involves a deeper, more personal examination of one's feelings and attitudes toward technology use. It is about understanding one's inherent biases and barriers to technology integration. Teachers expressed, "Introspection has made me aware of my reluctance towards new tech tools, which I am now overcoming," indicating how self-awareness leads to personal growth. Another said, "Through introspection, I realized that fear of failure was holding me back from experimenting with new software," showcasing how personal insights can address emotional barriers to technology adoption. Responses such as "Introspection helps me align my tech use with my educational philosophy" and "It is through introspection that I recognize the need for balance between technology and traditional methods" further underline its importance in thoughtful technology integration.

Theme 3. Critique

Critique involves critically analyzing the use of technology, personally and by peers, to identify areas of improvement and innovation. This could include peer reviews, student feedback, or self-assessment. One teacher shared, "Critiquing my tech-based lessons helps me improve and innovate continuously," emphasizing the role of critique in personal development. Another mentioned, "Peer critique sessions have been invaluable for refining the digital tools I use in class," reflecting how collaborative critique enhances technological practices. Further insights include, "I encourage my students to critique the tech tools we use, which helps me adjust their use," and "Critique from my mentor has prompted significant changes in how I integrate apps in teaching," showcasing how critique fosters a dynamic and responsive teaching environment.

Theme 4. Personal Voice

Personal voice is about expressing individual perspectives and advocating for personal and professional needs in technology usage. It reflects teachers' ability to influence C.P.D. strategies and educational technology policies. Teachers stated, "Using my voice, I have advocated for more technology training at our school," demonstrating how expressing needs can lead to enhanced support. Another said, "I express my concerns and successes with technology in staff meetings, which has led to better tech support," highlighting the impact of personal advocacy on resource allocation. Other responses like, "My voice helps shape the tech policies in our school, ensuring they meet our actual needs," and "Speaking up about the effectiveness of certain tools has influenced our school's tech purchases" illustrate the power of personal voice in shaping educational environments.

Theme 5. Comprehensive Discussion

These themes collectively emphasize the dynamic and reflective nature of the generative change model in technology integration within C.P.D. Teachers who engage in reflection and introspection develop a deeper understanding of their technology use, leading to more effective and personalized teaching strategies. Critique, both given and received, enhances this process by introducing external perspectives and feedback, which refine and improve practice. Finally, leveraging personal voice enables teachers to advocate for necessary changes and resources, ensuring that technology integration is effective and responsive to their needs. This holistic approach promotes individual teacher growth and drives innovative C.P.D. strategies sensitive to the evolving landscape of educational technology.

Developed Framework Implementation

Figure 1. Framework for C.P.D. Implementation

Framework Overview

Institutions should adopt the developed framework emphasizing reciprocal determinism, behavioral capability, observational learning, reinforcements, and personal factors as core components. This framework should serve as a guide for integrating technology in a manner that is sensitive to the needs and capacities of teachers.

Practical Application

Implement the framework by initiating pilot programs that allow for iterative feedback and adjustments. This approach ensures that the framework can evolve based on classroom experiences and emerging technological trends.

Enhanced Training Programs Comprehensive Training

Develop and implement training programs aligned with the framework, focusing on the technical aspects of technology use and the pedagogical strategies that optimize its use in the classroom.

Skill Development

Include modules on critical assessment of technology tools, digital literacy, and data privacy to ensure that teachers are not only users of technology but also critics and innovators.

Foster a Supportive Culture

Encouragement of Innovation

Schools should actively promote a culture that values and encourages innovation through technology. This can be facilitated by recognizing and rewarding teachers who effectively integrate technology into their teaching.

Peer Learning Networks

Establish communities of practice that enable teachers to share their experiences, learn from one another, and collaboratively solve problems related to technology use.

Policy and Infrastructure Support Investment in Infrastructure

Ensure that adequate digital infrastructure is in place to support the widespread use of technology in teaching and learning, including reliable internet access and up-to-date hardware.

Policy Frameworks

Develop clear policies that support the sustainable integration of technology in education, including funding models, professional development allowances, and support staff for technical maintenance and troubleshooting.

Further Research and Evaluation: Broader Studies

Conduct research with diverse educational settings and a broader geographic scope to validate and refine the framework.

Longitudinal Impact Studies: Implement longitudinal studies to assess the long-term impact of the framework on teacher performance and student learning outcomes.

Feedback Mechanisms and Continuous Improvement

Iterative Feedback: Establish mechanisms for regular feedback from teachers using the framework to refine and improve the training and resources provided continually.

Adaptability to Change: Ensure that the framework remains flexible enough to adapt to rapid technological changes and the evolving needs of educators.

Conclusions

Based on the study results, several key conclusions have been derived. The study is grounded in Social Cognitive Theory (S.C.T.), emphasizing the interaction between personal, behavioral, and environmental factors. This theoretical foundation is particularly suited for exploring the dynamics of Continuing Professional Development (C.P.D.), as it provides a nuanced understanding of the barriers and enablers in technological adoption among teachers. The utilization of the Generative Change Model further enhances this approach, offering a strategic method for managing the complexities involved in educational change. The model's focus on adaptation through iterative testing and scaling of new ideas (probes) is especially relevant in the context of the rapid technological changes impacting educational environments.

The study effectively positions teachers at the core of C.P.D. initiatives. By concentrating on their perspectives, the research acknowledges the crucial role teachers play in the successful integration of technology into education, ensuring that C.P.D. frameworks

are practical and applicable.

In light of these findings, several recommendations are proposed. Institutions are encouraged to provide continuous and dynamic training programs aligned with the technological needs and pedagogical goals of today's educators. These programs should aim to enhance technological proficiency and integrate these skills into effective teaching practices. Additionally, schools should foster an environment that encourages innovation, supporting teachers as they experiment with new technologies. This support could include administrative backing, peer mentoring, and the creation of learning communities where teachers can share experiences and solutions.

Educational policymakers must also ensure that schools have the digital infrastructure to support the proposed C.P.D. framework, including adequate hardware, software, internet access, and policies that encourage and reward innovative teaching practices. Further research should be conducted to assess the long-term effectiveness of the C.P.D. framework across different educational settings and demographic groups, providing insights into its broader applicability and sustainability.

Robust feedback mechanisms should be established to continuously gather input from teachers regarding the usability and effectiveness of the C.P.D. activities, with this feedback being used to make ongoing adjustments to the programs and support provided. Finally, the C.P.D. framework should be designed with flexibility in mind, allowing it to adapt to the rapid changes in technology and teaching methodologies. Implementing the framework in phases, starting with pilot projects, would allow for feedback and adjustment, ultimately refining the framework based on direct input from teachers.

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